

An open science dashboard for the biomedical community: a user-centered design

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Abstract

The adoption of UNESCO's *Recommendations on Open Science* cemented open science's (OS) position as a global science policy. Despite the recognition of its importance, policymakers often do not typically monitor adherence with their policies (Larivière & Sugimoto, 2018). This research-in-progress paper presents the development of an automated biomedical OS dashboard to track practices at the institutional level. The development of the dashboard follows a user-centered design. We were able to successfully automate, using primarily open source tools, a total of 9/19 open science practices identified from a community-consensus Delphi study (Cobey et al., 2023). Each of these practices achieved greater than 85% reliability compared to a manual extraction exercise used to validate the automation of each OS practice. Results from the usability testing indicate that users find the information clear and easy to understand, with modifications made to the dashboard to improve interpretation of metrics and usability.

1. Introduction

Open science is an umbrella term reflecting the movement and various practices to make scientific research, when appropriate, openly accessible, transparent, reproducible, and inclusive (UNESCO, 2021). Acknowledging the benefits of open science, governments, public funders, and international organizations, have implemented a range of policy mandates and guidelines to foster its implementation. In November 2021, UNESCO (2021) adopted its *Recommendation on Open Science*, cementing open science's position as a global science policy priority. UNESCO is urging its 193 member states to take collective action to achieve open science globally. The recommendations emphasize the importance of monitoring the adoption of practices in achieving this.

Despite the recognition of its importance, efforts are falling short on widespread adoption of open science. Notably, policymakers often do not typically monitor adherence with their open policies, a possible explanation for the failed implementation of open science adoption (Larivière & Sugimoto, 2018). At the same time, monitoring open science practices for external research assessment requirements have largely been focused on individual researcher actions and the unintended consequences have not been trivial and likely has led to adverse effects (Sugimoto & Larivière, 2018). Previous reports, including *Harnessing the Metric Tide*, strongly urge that indicators be co-designed and co-managed with those affected by them (Curry et al., 2022).

With this context in mind, we began our vision to create an institutional open science dashboard specific to biomedical research by bringing together 80 representatives from 20 institutions worldwide (Haustein et al., 2022). This consensus project led to 19 community-informed open science practices to monitor (Cobey et al, 2023). This research-in-progress paper presents the next stage of the project, the development of an automated biomedical research open science dashboard to track practices at the institutional level. We report on the findings of the multi-stage pilot project, including data collection, indicator validation, and user testing in the development of the dashboard.

2. Method

The development of the dashboard follows a user-centered design, including defining community requirements, identifying open data sources, validating indicators, and user testing evaluation (Figure 1).

Figure 1: User-centered design of the biomedical dashboard

We sought to develop the dashboard using open-source process pipelines and text mining algorithms for fetching, processing and analyzing data about academic research. The Dashboard piloted data processing workflows and functionality using publications from the Montreal Neurological Institute (“the Neuro”) published between 2009 - 2022 (N=3606).

The data in the dashboard is a subset of Curtin University's Open Knowledge Initiative's (COKI) Academic Observatory (Hosking et al., 2023), a data collection pipeline which fetches and synthesises data about research publications from multiple sources, including OpenAlex, Crossref metadata, Unpaywall, and the Research Organization Registry (ROR). The dashboard also utilizes Open Data Detection in Publications (ODDPub) code, a text mining algorithm that parses a set of publications to detect which publications disseminated Open Data or Open Code (Riedel et al., 2020). To enrich the dataset, customized open-source code was also used to extract metadata from clinicaltrials.gov via the Aggregate Analysis of ClinicalTrials.gov (AACT) Database.

We undertook a validation exercise to determine the accuracy of the automation of each of the open science practices in the dashboard. A 15% random sample (n=540) of article DOIs were chosen from our set of Neuro research articles. Bibliographic metadata pertaining to the open science practices from each article in the validation dataset was extracted using Covidence (RRID:SCR_016484). Two researchers independently manually screened the articles and extracted information on open science practices from the data validation subsample with discrepancies resolved by consensus. The full list of screening procedures is outlined in our protocol (Ripp et al., 2023).

In keeping with our community-centered approach, once our dashboard had been developed and validated, we re-engaged our community partners through a user-testing session to obtain their feedback on what we had created. To do so, 25 of our original community partners for our Delphi study contributed to a 1.5-hour user-testing focus group. User testing consisted of an A/B test as well as structure questions on user experience. The notes were organized, managed, and coded using Excel. Each question asked was coded independently. Data was reviewed and we developed a preliminary codebook using a deductive thematic analysis.

To better understand the breadth of practices at institutions, we conducted an interview study among our partners to understand what processes they have in place to track research outputs. We interviewed representatives from 10 of our initial 20 institutions involved in the Delphi and asked them about their use of research management systems or frameworks.

3. Results

We were able to successfully automate a total of 9/19 open science practices, with each of these practices achieving greater than 85% reliability compared to a manual extraction exercise used to validate the automation of each open science practice. We report the performance measures of the automated calculated indicators in the dashboard for open access status, availability of preprint, ORCID identifiers for authors, acknowledgement of funding source, and availability of open data and open code, as summarized in Table 1. For this, we compared the results from the manual screening to the results available in the dataset curated by the COKI pipeline.

The discrepancy between manual validation of funding and automated detection is in the inherent way it was implemented. Manual validation reviewed full-text document for the inclusion of a statement on funding, whereas the dashboard reports whether publisher metadata from Crossref included a funding acknowledgement. Therefore, of the practices automated, the indicator of funding acknowledge is underrepresented.

Table 1: Summary of validation results and description for indicators of the dashboard.

Practice	N (% correct)	Description
Open access	486 (90%)	Automated OA Type designation of publication open, other platform open, and both was correctly returned (N=540)
Preprints	514 (95%)	Automated detection of preprints (N=540)
Use of ORCID	490 (91%)	Validation reviewed publisher website and full-text document for ORCID attributed to author's affiliated with the Neuro. Whereas, the dashboard reports publication DOI appear in any publication author's ORCID record on orcid.org, including non-Neuro authors. (N=540)
Funder statements	305 (56%)	Validation reviewed full-text document for the inclusion of a statement on funding. Whereas, the dashboard reports whether publisher metadata from Crossref include a funding acknowledgement. (N=540)
Open data	366 (91%)	ODDpub algorithm correctly identified publications mentions of sharing of any open data (N=402, ODDpub did not screen all publication, primarily those designated as closed)
Open code	340 (85%)	ODDpub algorithm correctly identified publications mentions of sharing of any open code (N=402, ODDpub did not screen all publication, primarily those designated as closed)

Usability testing asked individual participants in a virtual whiteboard session to complete an A/B test to select the most appropriate dashboard landing page and answer a series of questions about the ease of using the dashboard, the quality of data visualizations, and overall feedback to improve the dashboard. This session provided valuable feedback on topics including how we could harmonize our reporting, use better visualizations, and more clearly describe our data filter functionality.

Following the successful piloting of the dashboard, we are working towards our vision to implement the tool in an initial group of biomedical institutions prior to scaling up more broadly. The interviews held will support the creation of an implementation handbook. We found significant heterogeneity in practices related to publication tracking, even when comparing seemingly similar types and sizes of institutions. In our sample, 9 of 10 institutions indicated they rely in part or completely on researchers to provide or verify their publication records, suggesting uptake of automatic harvesting from databases is not sufficient. We are nonetheless encouraged by the fact that 8 out of 10 institutions reported using ORCIDs, suggesting that greater adoption of this tool by researchers could harmonize reporting with increased researcher uptake and authentication. Just 1 of the 10 institutions reported tracking an open science practice beyond open access publication status, suggesting that our tool fills a gap in current monitoring.

4. Looking ahead

Our biomedical open science dashboard provides a pragmatic approach to equip institutions with the tool to monitor open science locally. Research institutions can act as effective enablers of change, providing an environment that reinforces and supports their researchers in their efforts to establish and implement open science practices. A key outcome of our work piloting the dashboard among an initial cohort of motivated institutions will be to document and report on the barriers and facilitators of the network as they implement the dashboard.

5. Bibliographic references

Cobey, K. D., Haustein, S., Brehaut, J., Dirnagl, U., Franzen, D. L., Hemkens, L. G., Presseau, J., Riedel, N., Strech, D., Alperin, J. P., Costas, R., Sena, E. S., van Leeuwen, T., Arden, C. L., Bacellar, I. O. L., Camack, N., Britto Correa, M., Buccione, R., Cenci, M. S., ... Moher, D. (2023). Community consensus on core open science practices to monitor in biomedicine. *PLoS Biology*, *21*(1), e3001949–e3001949.

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3001949>

COKI. (n.d.) *The Academic Observatory*. Retrieved April 5, 2024, from

<https://openknowledge.community/home/observatory/>

Curry, S., Gadd, E., & Wilsdon, J. (2022). *Harnessing the Metric Tide: Indicators, infrastructures & priorities for UK responsible research assessment*. Research on Research Institute. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.21701624.v2>

Haustein, S., Cobey, K., Neylon, C., Riedel, N., Franzen, D., Alperin, J.P., Dirnagl, U., & Moher, D. (2022). User-centred design in indicator development: Involving the biomedical community in building an open science dashboard. *Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Science, Technology and Innovation Indicators*, Granada, Spain.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6948166>

Hosking, R., Diprose, J. P., Roelofs, A., Chien, T., Massen-Hane, A., Smith, K. R., Handcock, R. N., Kramer, B., Napier, K. R., Tonti-Filippini, J., Montgomery, L., & Neylon, C. (2023). *Academic Observatory Workflows* [Computer software].

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6366694>

Larivière, V., & Sugimoto, C. R. (2018). Do authors comply when funders enforce open access to research? *Nature (London)*, 562(7728), 483–486. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-018-07101-w>

Riedel, N., Kip, M., & Bobrov, E. (2020). ODDPub – a Text-Mining Algorithm to Detect Data Sharing in Biomedical Publications. *Data Science Journal*, 19(1), 42-. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-042>

Ripp, C., Armond, A. C. V., Cobey, K. D., & Haustein, S. (2023, July 19). *Developing an open science dashboard for biomedical institutions*. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/TJCWG>

Sugimoto, C. R., & Larivière, V. (2018). *Measuring research: What everyone needs to know*. Oxford University Press.

UNESCO. (2021). *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science*. <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMMH8546>

Open science practices

Project materials for the biomedical dashboard, including protocol registrations, have been made available on the Open Science Framework (OSF) DOI: 10.17605/OSF.IO/JM8WG.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization: All authors ; Methodology: KDC, ACVA, RNH, CN, CR, DLF, VN, GP, MS-H, TLW, MAA, DM, SH; Software: RNH,CN,DLF,VN,MS-H; Validation: KDC, ACVA, RNH, CN, CR, DLF, VN, MS-H, GP; Formal Analysis: KDC, ACVA, CR, MAA; Investigation: KDC, ACVA, CR, MAA; Resources: RHN, CN, DLF, VN, MS-H; Data Curation: KDC, ACVA, RHN, CN, CR, DLF, VN, MS-H; Writing-Original Draft: CR; Writing- Review & Editing: All authors; Visualization: RHN, CN; Supervision: KDC, CN, SH; Project Administration: KDC, SH; Funding Acquisition: KDC, CN, DLF, SH.

Competing interests

KDC is co-chair of DORA.

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